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HSbooster.eu
Horizon Standardisation Booster

Interim Call Monitoring Report

Deliverable

2.2

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Glossary

Terminology/Acronym	Description
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
EAG	External Advisory Group
EPE	External Pool of Evaluators
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
OC	Open Call
OCB	Open Call Board
PPC	Pay-Per-Click
R&I	Research and Innovation
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TSP	Trust SOP Platform
TWG	Technical Working Group
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an in-depth overview of the open calls management and premium service delivery procedures established by HSbooster.eu. This project has developed a robust methodology to offer consultancy services to European Commission funded R&I projects through an Open Call system. This document is the first of two reports that present the main statistics and outcomes of the open calls for external experts and projects.

The HSbooster.eu project has received over 70 project applications and recruited more than 150 experts so far, providing valuable insights into the challenges and barriers to applications and service delivery. This document showcases the platform's open calls management and premium service delivery procedures and the importance of monitoring tools to ensure the successful running of the services. The report covers the external pool of experts, project applications and eligibility, expert and project matching, and service delivery procedures. Additionally, the report presents a monitoring tool to track the progress of the service delivery and identifies lessons learned and contingencies for future reference. The project is committed to delivering a rich set of recommendations for the future EU standardisation booster service, drawing from its lessons learned. The project team will continue to gather insights and implement recommendations to ensure the success of this pilot.

1. Introduction and scope of document

This document presents the current status of the Open Calls (OC) management and premium service delivery at M12, detailing the methodology and procedures in place as well as the challenges and contingency plans adopted to overcome them. It contains the main outcomes, statistics and relevant facts of the External Pool of Experts (EPE) and projects OC and the underlying digital processes starting with the call application processes and ending with the service delivery monitoring. As part of the processes hereafter described, it is important also to highlight that the HSbooster.eu consortium has provided assistance to applicants through the provision of hands-on support, when requested, during the entire OC process. This degree of assistance was needed, on one side, to guarantee the complete accuracy and fairness of the evaluation cycle and, on the other side, to help applicants to correctly submit applications aligned with the scope of the project.

- This deliverable is connected to D4.2 – Initial Standards Impact Report – and they are submitted in the same period. While this deliverable focuses on the procedures and overview of activities from a process perspective, D4.2 elaborates on preliminary evidence and impact from the ongoing services and details measures to maximise the results of the processes here described;
- The deliverable is also related to D3.1 - Services Matrix, as it details the premium service, i.e. one of the services provided by the project;
- The document connects with D2.1 – HSbooster.eu website, D4.1 – Stakeholder Engagement plan and D5.1 - Initial plan for dissemination, exploitation, communication, and training activities, as the communication and engagement tools described in these connected deliverables are all key, on one side, to attract projects and experts and, on the other side, to manage all digital processes connected to the delivery of standardisation services and the management of applications via the Trust SOP Platform (TSP);
- This deliverable anticipates D2.3 — Final Call Monitoring Report, which will provide an update of this midterm overview, completing the activities here started and implementing the identified recommendations, as well as any new procedures that will have to be implemented in the second half of the project;
- Moreover, the deliverable provides valuable preliminary input which will be refined and embedded into the final D5.2 – Recommendations Report, framing the future HSbooster.eu Framework Contract;
- Lastly, it complies with the Data Protection and Management Plan outlined in D1.2 – Data Management Plan (DMP).

1.1 Structure

The document is structured as follows:

- **Section 1 “Introduction and scope of the document”**. This section provides the context of the work being carried out on the HSbooster.eu premium service delivery and open calls monitoring as well as the relation of this document with other project deliverables;
- **Section 2 “HSbooster.eu Service Delivery Machine”**. This section offers a snapshot of the main processes and mechanisms that have been put in place to practically implement the HSbooster.eu’s mission of delivering consultancy services to applicant R&I projects;

- **Sections from 3 to 7** detail every phase and step of the HSbooster.eu Service Delivery Machine, starting with EPE and projects application, including matching of projects and experts, service delivery and monitoring;
- **Section 8 “Lessons learned and contingencies”**. It discusses the main challenges and problems encountered and presents the planned mitigation and corrective actions;
- **Section 9 “Recommendations”**. This summarises the learning points stemming from the work that has been conducted so far and delineates recommendations for improvement in the second half of the project lifetime;
- **Section 10 “Conclusions”**. It outlines the main key messages of the deliverable and the next steps for future development.

2. The HSbooster.eu Service Delivery Machine

As part of its 24-month mission, the HSbooster.eu project has successfully designed and implemented a rigorous methodology to deliver up to 500 premium services to H2020, DEP and HE R&I projects. The premium services are made available via an Open Call system which allows both standardisation experts and projects to apply for and receive consultancy services. The HSbooster.eu team has developed a detailed process for the delivery of these services, which involves the following steps:

- **EPE Applications:** Already at M2 of the project (May 2022), an expression of interest was published and promoted to collect interest from standardisation professionals. Later, starting from M03, applications from standardisation experts in various fields were opened. Once experts apply, via an online form at HSbooster.eu, the received applications are reviewed by the HSbooster.eu team and the profiles of the experts are analysed to assess their eligibility. If the experts are eligible, they are ranked by at least two partners and those who get a vote over a set threshold enter the External Pool of Experts (EPE) as their profile gets also published on the HSbooster.eu website.
- **Project Applications:** In M4 (July 2022), the open call for projects was also launched. Once the project representative submits an application, the HSbooster.eu team evaluates its eligibility and, if the project is eligible, it enters the pipeline to be matched with a suitable expert.
- **Matching:** The matching process is based on a thorough analysis of the needs of each project and the experience and profile of available experts. DCU, a partner of the consortium, is responsible for proposing the matching, which is then discussed and approved by the rest of the consortium in fortnightly Open Call Board meetings. Once the matching is approved, the designated expert is contacted, informed, and asked to sign a contract.
- **Service delivery:** The service delivery process begins with an introductory call between the HSbooster.eu team and each expert. During this call, preliminary queries are addressed, a demonstration of the TSP (the tool used to track and manage the service delivery process) is performed, and the next steps are explained. The service officially starts with a kick-off call, which the expert generally sets up with the assigned project. The service is delivered via meetings (up to four) and should be concluded within three months of the kick-off call.
- **Service monitoring:** The HSbooster.eu team monitors the progress of the service delivery process via a monitoring tool. It addresses requests and concerns from both experts and projects and collects feedback for improvement, both informally (via discussions and emails) and formally (via satisfaction surveys).
- **Service closure and payment of experts:** Upon completion of the service, the experts submit a report with a description of the activities conducted. The HSbooster.eu team is then responsible for assessing the quality of the submitted reports and either confirm closure and proceed with the payment or request needed amendments and corrections to the expert who will need to re-submit the report to ensure adequate quality. When a quality check is passed the payment is performed.

Overall, the HSbooster.eu project has developed a comprehensive methodology for the delivery of premium standardisation services to R&I projects, which is revised upon need as soon as new instances occur. This process, combined with the monitoring and feedback mechanisms, ensures that the services are adjusted to meet the needs of both experts and projects. The table below provides details of the project organisation and the responsible partner for each activity of the Open Calls and service delivery management and monitoring.

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Phase	Activity	Partner Responsible	Means	Notes
EPE Open call management	EPE application – technical setup	COMMpla	Platform	
EPE Open call management	EPE application – data analysis for statistics	COMMpla	Excel sheets	
EPE Open call management	EPE application – eligibility check of experts	DCU	Platform	
EPE Open call management	EPE voting	<p>DCU is responsible for the allocations of eligible experts to two partners.</p> <p>Each partner is responsible to complete the voting of the experts it has been assigned</p>	<p>e-mail to partners</p> <p>voting on the platform</p>	The voting is partially done automatically by the TSP for quantitative and objective criteria (Roles and Years of experience in specific TWGs, gender balance). Manual voting from partners is instead required for qualitative criteria (participation in TWGs, other expertise and professional background)
EPE Open call management	EPE ranking	COMMpla	Platform	The ranking is calculated automatically by the TSP based on the scores assigned in the voting phase
Project Open call management	Project application – technical setup	COMMpla	Platform	
Project Open call management	Project application – data analysis for statistics	COMMpla	Excel sheets	
Project Open call management	Project application – eligibility check of projects	DCU	Platform	
Matching	Suggested matching of Experts and Projects	DCU	Excel sheets	
Matching	Pre-assignment of an Expert to a Project	COMMpla	e-mails	Pre-assignment is communicated via e-mail to the experts who need to confirm their availability to start the service
Matching	Revision of matching	OCB	Excel sheets	In the fortnightly calls any needs to revise the matching (e.g. due to expert

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				unavailability, conflict of interest, or other) is discussed and addressed
Service delivery	Contract signature (between expert and HSbooster.eu)	COMMpla	e-mails	
Service delivery	Direct Provision of premium services to selected projects	DS	Meetings	DS directly delivered the service in the initial phase of the project to test the platform and gather more direct feedback. Moreover, DS may deliver additional services over the lifespan of HSbooster.eu to cover for any missing requested experience in the EPE
Service delivery	Introductory call with expert	COMMpla: Dec 2022 – Feb 2023 SGS: March 2023 Onwards	Meetings	The call aims to explain to the experts: 1) What is expected from the expert and the project 2) How the platform works 3) Processes and procedures 4) Examples and templates for experts 4) Next steps
Service delivery	Support to projects and experts	SGS	e-mails, meetings	SGS is the main contact point to collect issues and requests. Once an issue or request is received (via e-mail), it is thoroughly evaluated and then assigned to the appropriate partner for resolution based on the type of request.
Service delivery	Support to project and experts in relation to Training materials	UoB	e-mails, meetings	

Service monitoring	Monitoring tool – technical setup	COMMpla	Platform	
Service monitoring – Time and quality management	Reminders to EPE, check that the services progress and conclude in time	SGS	e-mails	
Service closure and payment	Initial quality check of final reports: verify that all sections are complete and have enough level of detail	SGS	e-mails, Platform	
Service closure and payment	Second round of quality check	All partners	e-mails, Platform	SGS allocates the reports which passed the initial quality check to each partner to perform a more in-depth review. The allocation is approved at each Open Call Board meeting
Service closure and payment	Approval of report	All partners	e-mails, Platform	Partners confirm the result of quality check with SGS that then prepares the list of experts that can be paid
Service closure and payment	Administrative closure of approved services and payment to experts	COMMpla	e-mails, Platform	

Table 1 - Open Calls, Service Delivery and Monitoring procedures and responsibilities

The following chapters will provide further details on the above steps as well as information and statistics on the status of applications and services.

3. External Pool of Experts (EPE)

3.1. Applications for EPE

3.1.1 EPE Application Form

Since its launch, the project website has hosted an **“Expression of interest”** form aimed at collecting questions and contacts from various stakeholders. In its initial structure on the landing page, the form could be filled in by both standardisation experts willing to apply for the EPE Open Call and by EU projects interested in finding more information about the standardisation services. The form collected information on the users, their organisations and the standardisation topics of interest/experience. All queries were addressed, contacted, informed of the next steps of the project and invited to attend the first official webinar of the project held on 31st May.

On 30th May, as the V1 of the website was launched with the Open Call for Experts.

The **Application for the EPE Open Call** is a continuously open call which helps the project recruit standardisation experts. Interested experts need to provide their contact information, affiliation, country of residence, and list their relevant experience, including relevant roles in SDOs, at European, national or international level. They should also indicate the topics or areas in which they can provide support.

Once the application form is submitted, a notification of receipt is sent to the applicant. In the website backend, the application form is actually a registration form that assigns the applicant the role of “EPE”. In an initial phase, the status of the applicant will appear as “blocked” until the eligibility check is performed by project partner DCU. Once the expert is considered eligible, their status becomes “active” and they can be contacted and receive assignments. If they are not eligible they are denied the EPE status but can keep their registration as community users in the platform, unless they resubmit the application addressing and solving the non-eligibility issues.

Following an analysis of the first batch of applications, a series of improvements in the data gathered were identified. Based on this, in M12 (March 2023) v2 of the EPE Open Call application form was published. This has improved the workflow and the quality of data collected facilitating the matching of projects to experts:

- The number of open call topics that the expert can select is now limited (up to 3) to avoid lack of specialisation or understanding of the excellence areas of the expert.
- Current and previous positions as well as academic qualifications need to be specifically described in the application form to make sure this information is available and standardised as it was not always fully present in the attached CVs.
- More details are asked with reference to the experts’ experience with standardisation bodies and their standardisation roles (e.g. number and title of Technical Committee, sub-committee, Working Group).
- An open box inviting the experts to tell us more about themselves and delineate reasons and motivations why they could contribute to HSbooster.eu to provide us with additional insights about the expert suitability for the role.
- The consensus to publish the EPE profile on the website (if eligible) is directly collected in this phase, while previously a dedicated message had to be sent to experts to get their approval for their profiles to be displayed online.

The image below displays the new EPE application form available at HSbooster.eu

Figure 1 - New version of EPE Application Form

3.1.2 Status of EPE Applications

As of May 15th, 2023, the HSbooster.eu project has received a total of **154 eligible applications** from External Pool of Experts (EPE) candidates. This number is in line with the project's target of recruiting 250+ experts by the end of the initiative. As illustrated in the figure below, the applications have good coverage of open call topics, and the experts possess many years of experience and occupy important roles in standardisation bodies. Approximately 25% of the applications come from women, which is in line with the gender balance situation amongst standardisation experts. [According to ISO](#), male participation in standardisation is twice as high as women's.

Figure 2 - EPE Applications statistics as of 15th May 2023 (N=154)

However, half of the EPE pool comes from Central Europe, highlighting the need to solicit and improve applications from underrepresented geographical areas. To address this issue, the consortium will engage with the External Advisory Group (EAG) to support the consortium in recruiting more experts by taking the following steps:

- Contacting National Standards Bodies in areas where applications from experts are lower.
- Identifying a set of events in geographical areas or topic domains that are underrepresented where the EAG consortium can attend and promote the EPE Open Call.

3.2. EPE Eligibility

Once an application is received, DCU performs an eligibility check. To this purpose, each profile and the application details are analysed to verify if there is the need to request for additional information, such as a missing resume, and the application is examined to assess the expert's suitability for the role. If the outcome of the eligibility check is successful, the expert is marked as “Eligible” in the STP and an automatic notification message is sent to inform the experts that they may be contacted to serve a project matching their areas of expertise. Once the experts are confirmed as eligible, EPE status in the platform is switched from “blocked” to “active” so that they can enter the platform, navigate and autonomously update their profile as needed.

3.3. EPE Voting and ranking

As soon as an expert becomes eligible, the TSP assigns a vote to their profile based on quantitative criteria, such as gender (female applicants are given a higher score to support their participation and selection and ensure gender balance given the lower number of female applicants). Nonetheless, there are certain qualitative criteria, e.g. related to specific roles, additional experience and background evaluation that the platform cannot perform on its own. Therefore, each expert is also voted by two partners who insert their vote and additional comments in the TSP. Once an expert has been fully voted, DCU is responsible for consolidating and closing the voting on the platform. If the submitted votes are not coherent (e.g. there is high variance or discordance in the voting), DCU flags the problem and invites the voting partners to reach an alignment. Unresolved cases are discussed at the first available OCB meeting with the rest of the consortium, or via an ad-hoc meeting where necessary. It is important to note that the voting scale has been revised to a range of 1 to 10 (previously 0.1 to 10) as a collective decision of the OCB. This change was made to ensure a more homogeneous voting process among all partners.

Figure 3 - EPE voting system

The assigned votes then automatically generate an expert ranking, which remains visible to the project consortium only, and is then used as a support during the project-expert matching phase.

The image below displays the **EPE voting system mechanism**:

4. Projects

4.1. Project Applications

4.1.1. Project Application Form

With the launch of the EPE open call, in June, a new Expression of interest form was created targeting only EU projects. These were collected until the official Open Call for projects also became available.

Similar to the EPE Application form, the Project Application form enables project representatives to apply for a premium service. Regarding the open call for projects, there was a shift in the project's approach, as it was initially planned to have five distinct open calls, each centred around a specific topic. However, after careful consideration and to foster a more dynamic and inclusive participation, it was decided to adopt a continuous open call framework, ensuring ongoing opportunities for engagement.

Once the application form is submitted, a notification of receipt is sent to the applicant. In the website backend, the application form is actually a registration form that assigns the applicant the role of "Project". In an initial phase, the status of the applicant will appear as "blocked" until the eligibility check is performed by project partner DCU. Once the project is considered eligible, their status becomes "active" and they can be contacted to start the service.

As done for the EPE, In M12 (March 2023) the **Project Open Call** (displayed below) was revised with improvements that were deemed appropriate to improve the workflow. The new version has the following updates:

- The number of open call topics that the project can select is now limited (up to 3) to allow better focus and align with the options given to the experts.
- More details are requested with reference to the project's interest in specific standardisation bodies and their standardisation roles (e.g. number and title of Technical Committee, sub-committee, Working Group). The question is aligned to the one present in the EPE application form to enable a better matching. Moreover, the projects are asked if they are interested in just using the identified standards in their project or also contributing to their development
- The consensus to publish the project profile on the website (if eligible) is directly collected in this phase, while previously a dedicated message had to be sent to project representatives to get their approval for their profiles to be displayed online.

The screenshot displays three sections of the application form:

- About your project:** Includes fields for Client Agreement Number, Project acronym, Full project name, Funding programmer, Please indicate the Call Topic ID, Project Website, and Project officer name.
- Open call topic:** Requests a maximum of three open call topics. It features a dropdown menu with a list of topics such as Health, COVID-19 vaccines, Needle-free and needle-based injection systems for medical use, COVID-19 vaccines, Aseptic processing, Medicine production, Respiratory equipment, and Resilience, measurement and resilience. Below this, it asks about the support the project requires and provides a short description of the project and its standardisation objectives.
- Which standards are you targeting?:** Asks if the applicant knows which standards or Technical Committee/Sub-committee/Working Groups they would like to engage with. It includes a dropdown for Standards, a field for the number of Technical Committee/Sub-committee/Working Group (with a full code example), and a field for the title of the Technical Committee/Sub-committee/Working Group. It also asks if the applicant would like to contribute to the work on this standard.

Figure 6 - New version of Project Application Form

4.1.2. Status of Project Applications

A total of **77 project eligible applications** were received as of 15th May 2023. This number is off track with respect to the expected target of delivering 500 premium services to projects, therefore a series

of actions have been identified to support the recruitment of projects and solicit more applications. The statistics for the applications received so far are summarised in the figure below.

Figure 7 - Project Applications statistics as of 15th May (N=77)

There is general alignment on the topics of interest between the projects and experts. Almost 40% of applications are from females representing an improved gender balance with respect to the EPE. In terms of geographical coverage, most of the applications come from Southern Europe, followed by Central Europe, while Eastern and Northern Europe are the least represented. Also, two thirds of applications derive from H2020 projects. While this can be expected as older and more mature projects are likely to have had more time to understand and define their possible contributions to standardisation and therefore be interested in HSbooster.eu, there is a need to recruit more projects especially from HE and when they are at earlier stages.

The following measures have been identified to support project applications, increasing their overall number and reinforcing those coming from least covered areas:

- Enrich our project database collecting information and contacts of all DEP, HE and H2020 projects as well as interacting with SDOs (e.g. CEN-CENELEC) to access projects they are in contact with.

- Scout projects mentioned in relevant EC documents or initiatives such as the ICT standardisation rolling plan.
- Exploit synergies with standards related initiatives like StandICT.eu or Stand4EU.
- Set-up Pay-Per-Click Campaigns (PPC) to improve visibility and positioning of the website and social media posts to attract more visits to our project application page.
- Identify a set of events, also in geographical areas or topic domains which are under-represented where the consortium or the EAG can attend and promote the Project Open Call.
- Create a “how to apply” video raising awareness on the services offered and motivating project representatives to submit their applications.

4.2. Project eligibility

Once a project application is received, DCU performs an eligibility check. Each application from projects is checked EC databases like CORDIS to verify it is a real project. The application is also analysed to verify that the requested service is appropriate and linked to standardisation activities.

If the outcome of the eligibility check is successful, the project is marked as “Eligible” in the STP and an automatic notification message is sent to inform the project representatives that they may be contacted to start the service once a suitable expert is identified. Once the projects become eligible, their profiles are published on the website in the project hub, shown in the figure below, where all the applicant projects are visible with information extracted from their application to showcase their standardisation needs. Also, the project status in the platform is switched from “blocked” to “active” so that project representatives can enter the platform, navigate and autonomously update their project pages as needed.

The figure shows two views of the Project Hub. On the left is the 'Project Hub' view, which displays a grid of 18 project cards, each with a logo and name. On the right is a 'Single project page' view, which provides detailed information for a specific project titled 'Project Name: A Circular Multilayer Plastic Approach for value retention of end-of-life multilayer films'. The single project page includes a description, a reason for applying to HSbooster.eu services, and a main standardisation interest section.

Figure 8 - Project Hub – Selected views of online pages

5. Expert and project matching

Both EPE and project application forms feed the matching process aimed at connecting projects and experts. The STP automatically suggests a preliminary list of suitable experts based on the ranking and some compatibility elements, e.g., main topics, sub-topics, SDOs, and query keys (extracted from the projects), to get accurate matching. A selection is then made by DCU on a case-by-case basis considering also qualitative criteria and the amount of projects already assigned to a given expert (see the figure below for example). The selected expert is then notified and the service can start upon acceptance and contract signature by the expert. Other experts are selected in case of unavailability.

The association between the expert and the project is formalised via the STP after the introductory call with the expert (see chapter 6) takes place. For each project the expert is selected from a list appearing on the right side of the page as shown in the figure below. Both the project and the expert receive a notification when the assignment is accepted by the expert. From this moment onwards, the experts and projects have access to their personal space that can be used to keep track of the service progress and the outcomes of the meetings.

Figure 9 - Project-Expert Matching page

Figure 10 - Project-Expert Matching page mechanism

As shown in the figure below, at the time of submitting this deliverable, 76 eligible applicant projects have been matched with an expert. A total number of 59 experts are involved (some experts can be assigned to more than one project based on their expertise and availability at the time they are contacted). Most of the selected experts have signed the contract, while 1 has received the contract. The remaining 3 are discussing details and providing information necessary for drafting the contract. The introductory call has been held or scheduled with all the experts who have signed the contract. When needed, reminders and solicitations have been sent to all the briefed experts to schedule the kick-off call with the assigned project and update promptly the information on the TSP where the monitoring tool allows checking the status of service delivery.

Premium Services - Project/Expert matching & services launched

Figure 11 - Status of projects matched, contracts and introductory calls with experts 15th May 2023

6. Service delivery procedures

The service delivery process is preceded by a series of administrative steps, namely:

- **Notification** (via e-mail) to experts about the assigned project
- **Acceptance** (via e-mail) of the service
- **Signature of the contract**

Among these, in particular, the **contract** regulates the remuneration to be provided (Financial Support to Third Parties) within the framework of the HSBooster.eu Horizon Europe Grant Agreement with the European Commission. The contract includes general terms and conditions and a code of conduct for delivery of the services and special provisions for the processing of any personal data that may come into the expert's possession, non-disclosure of any information made available to the expert by the project or the HSBooster.eu team, as well as the mandatory flow-down of provisions imposed by HSBooster.eu's Grant Agreement with the European Commission

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The foreseen remuneration for the expert's effort for each Premium Service is fixed at a rate of €400 per day, up to a total 2 days or €800, per Premium Service. The contract also specifies that the payment will be made on completion of each service upon submission and acceptance of the Report that the expert must fill in in all its sections. More precisely, the HSBooster.eu team (COMMpla) will send the expert a Payment Request Form for the expert to sign and return for payment upon acceptance of the report.

Once the contract is signed, an **introductory call** of approximately 30 min is scheduled as a one-to-one meeting with the expert. During the call, the expectations are discussed and instructions are given to the expert for the successful completion of the service within a timeframe of 3 months starting from the moment the expert and the project representative meet for the first time. The following steps follow the training call with the expert and are discussed and explained during the call itself:

- **Access to the Service delivery platform** and contacts with the project: a demo is organised to check any technical issues (and solve them). The platform is shown to the expert and the contacts and details of the project are provided.
- **Delivery of the service** (first meeting, intermediate meetings, formal advice, final meeting): the service then starts with the expert contacting the project and scheduling the meetings for the consultancy. The HSbooster.eu team are available to support both the project and the expert in case of any issues and solicits the progress of activities if needed.
- **Submission of online report and evaluation survey:** over the course of the service, the expert can start completing the EPE report detailing all the activities planned and performed and providing an assessment of the progress made by the project. The report can be accessed by the project representative as well. Both the expert and the project are requested to provide feedback on their experience and are solicited to submit an evaluation questionnaire at the end of activities
- **Quality check of submitted report:** Upon submission of the report, SGS oversees the distribution of reports to all partners to ensure that each partner can verify the completeness and comprehensiveness of the report assigned to them for review. If the report meets the quality standards, the process moves to the final stage. However, if the submitted report is of inadequate quality, the expert is requested to revise and complete it based on the feedback provided by the partner responsible for the quality check. SGS coordinates the process to ensure that the revised report is resubmitted for a second review.
- **Service closure and payment:** Once all the procedures above have been completed and the submitted report passes quality check, as per the steps described in table 1, the service is considered closed and the payment is made to the expert by COMMpla

All the steps here listed can be managed via the STP as shown in the screenshots below.

Figure 12 - Selected views of the service delivery platform

The main steps in this process are accompanied by a series of “status changes” in the platform to manage and monitor the meeting services. Some of these “status changes” are automatic i.e. these occur when the expert accepts the service or submits their report, while others are made manually by the Partners i.e. following verification of the expert reports. In some cases the “status change” generates an automatic message to inform that a step has been completed or to trigger an action required. The following table 2 provides a detailed overview of the steps and their respective statuses on the platform, along with the associated notifications. Additionally, Figure 13 summarises the main phases and actors involved in the workflow.

Step/status in the platform	Description	Automatic message
EPE- Pending	A new expert submits an application and awaits to be evaluated	A notification is sent to the HSbooster.eu team
EPE- Eligible	The Expert passes the eligibility check performed by DCU	A notification is sent to the expert and to HSbooster.eu team
EPE- Non eligible	The Expert does not pass the eligibility check performed by DCU	A notification is sent to the expert and to HSbooster.eu team
EPE - Voted	The Expert has been voted by at least two Consortium partners	No notification
Project - Pending	A new project submits an application and awaits to be evaluated	A notification is sent to the HSbooster.eu team
Project - Eligible	The project passes the eligibility check performed by DCU	A notification is sent to the project and to HSbooster.eu team
Project - Non eligible	The Project does not pass the eligibility check performed by DCU	A notification is sent to the project and to HSbooster.eu team
Matching expert-project: selected	The HSbooster.eu Team formally assigns the project to the identified expert via the platform (after the signature of the contract and the introductory call with the expert)	A notification to confirm the selection is sent to the expert

Matching expert-project: approved	The expert formally accepts the service in TSP (after the signature of the contract and the introductory call with the HSbooster.eu team). This results in an automatic status change to “APPROVED”	Notification of the project and expert match goes both to the expert and the project (with information on how to access their respective platform pages)
Matching expert-project: Not approved	The expert rejects the service on the platform if they are unable to accept the service following the intro call for any reason. This results in an automatic status change to “NOT APPROVED”	Notification is sent to HSbooster.eu team to select an alternative expert
Report Submitted	The expert indicates on the platform that they have completed the service and submits the report. This results in an automatic status change in the platform to “REPORT SUBMITTED”	Notification is sent to the project and the expert to confirm that the report has been submitted, as well as to SGS to trigger the verification and project closure
Check 1 Check 1 complete	SGS performs a preliminary check on the report in the platform to confirm that this satisfies the minimum quality criteria, namely: (i) all compulsory sections of the report have been completed; (ii) there is a sufficient amount of text pertinent to the work carried out by the expert in each section. SGS then EITHER a) manually changes the status of the service to “CHECK 1 COMPLETE” and identifies a partner to perform the more detailed quality check OR b) rejects the report. In the case of b) the expert needs to resubmit the report again for Check 1.	No automatic notification in case of approval, as the activity of identifying a second Partner for Quality Control will be managed by SGS via e-mail, or at the first available OCB meeting. Notification in the case of rejection whereby a dialogue box will also appear to state the reasons for rejection to go back to the expert to make the necessary adjustments and resubmit the report. Rejections would apply if the minimum quality criteria are not satisfied
Check 2 Check 2 Complete	The partner identified by SGS to perform the second quality check completes this and EITHER a) manually changes the status of the service to “CHECK 2 COMPLETE” OR b) rejects the report. In case of b) process reverts to Check 1 step	Notification to SGS that the Check 2 is complete, or the report is rejected.
OCB Approved	A list of the approved reports, visible to all Partners via the platform, is ratified and minuted at the OCB meeting where the content of service will be reviewed. After the OCB meeting SGS sends the list of approved services to COMMpla to trigger payment. COMMpla manually changes the status of the service to “OCB Approved”	No automatic notification. At the end of each meeting, as this process is managed via e-mail and during the OCB meetings.
In payment	COMMpla sends a payment form to the expert and manually changes the status on the platform to “IN PAYMENT”	Notification to the expert that the service delivered has been approved and is in payment
Paid	Once the expert has been paid, COMMpla manually changes the status on the platform to “PAID”	Notification to the expert that they have been paid

Table 2 - Summary of service status and notifications via the TSP (Trust SOP Platform)-

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Figure 13 - Platform workflow

7. Monitoring tool

The progress of activities related to the service delivery are continuously monitored with the help of a service monitoring tool, whose preview is offered in the figure below, and via one-to-one interactions with experts and projects.

SOP services status
 You can see only approved, closed and completed services

ID	PROJECT	EPE	STATUS	APPROV DATE UTC	MEETING 1 SET/DONE	MEETING 1 DATE	MEETING 2 SET/DONE	MEETING 2 DATE	MEETING 3 SET/DONE	MEETING 3 DATE	ADVICE	FINAL MEETING SET/DONE	FINAL MEETING DATE	SERVICE COMPLETE
146_80	CyberSEAS	Wolfgang Ziegler	completed		DONE	2023-02-15	DONE	2023-03-08	DONE	2023-04-21	DONE	DONE	2023-04-26	DONE
186_162	AFC4Hydro	Seyed Mohammad Mousavi Agah	approved		SET	2023-02-21								
105_175	AI-PROFICIENT	Ilona Anna Cieslik	approved		DONE	2023-02-24	DONE	2023-03-17						

Figure 14 - Service monitoring tool

Beyond the quantitative check on the number of services started and on the progress of activities, also a qualitative evaluation of the online reports written by the experts is performed. More details about the main contents and impacts of services being delivered is contained in the D4.2 - Initial Standards Impact Report. SGS, leading the premium service monitoring task, checks periodically the information reported by the experts on the STP and signal those cases where:

- The report has not been started even if the first meeting (or more) already took place.
- The information in the report is too generic or unclear.
- Details about the dates of the hold/scheduled meetings are not provided.

The critical cases are marked and tracked in a monitoring file which is updated twice a week. SGS is responsible for collecting the issues and describing them in the file, while assigning them to the most appropriate partner who will act to resolve the issue. An excerpt of the issue monitoring file is presented in the figure below.

Issue #	DATE	EXPERT	PROJECT	PROBLEM	CATEGORY
1	2.03.23	Paola Amato	Reffect Africa/HZValue	Expert could not connect to platform.	Platform
2	2.03.23	Rusne Juozapaitiene	MEDINA	Expert Rusne Juozapaitiene asks about consequences of renouncing after the first meeting. Maria G. has asked for it to the partners on 3/03, still not answered	Generic
3	3.03.23	Argyro Chatzopoulou	LOCARD	Expert Argyro Chatzopoulou asks us if there is a conflict of interest, because her project representative (of project LOCARD) is an external reviewer of other project that she is participating - Revire-. Solved by M. Giuffrida: there is not conflict, continue as planned.	Generic

Figure 15 - Issue monitoring file

As part of the monitoring activities, statistics about the status of the applications from both experts and projects with details on the gender, geographical locations, topics covered, type of organisation and SDOs of interest, are produced and updated every two weeks as shown in sections 3.1.2 and 4.1.2. The update of the statistics is managed by COMMpla, relying on excel spreadsheets downloaded from the HSbooster.eu STP which is updated in real time with the latest available applications. The figure below presents the excel spreadsheet containing the data from the STP which is used to create the statistics dashboard.

Figure 16 - Applications Spreadsheets for statistics

8. Lessons learned and contingencies

Over its first year of activity, the project has faced several challenges which have sometimes caused unexpected delays. However, these have been addressed with corrective measures and provided valuable insights and learning points for the purposes of this project that, being a pilot, needs testing different routes to assess the most desirable strategy to support standardisation activities of projects in an effective way.

The present chapter lists the most important challenges faced and the mitigation actions identified:

- TSP technical development:** One of the first and most critical challenges encountered lies in the technical development of the TSP underlying the whole open calls management and service delivery digital processes. While the initial functionalities of the platform, i.e. the ones

allowing the registration of EPE and projects as user profile, the EPE voting and ranking, were delivered on time, the service delivery component that allows experts to access information, schedule meetings and fill-in the report underwent a delay due to:

- **Time needed to design the premium service concept:** this consisted of various iterations, improvements and modifications. For instance, initially the service was supposed to be bound to a pre-defined number of meetings, while subsequently it was deemed more appropriate to link the service only to a defined set of expected outcomes and activities, leaving the number of meetings more flexible. Also, the structure of the online report, the material to be made available, the texts of all the messaging and communications, the visualisation features were discussed at length and various options were considered before selecting the one to be implemented.
- **Technical implementation:** the effort required to implement the TSP proved to be higher than what initially estimated.

While these issues have caused a delay in the actual start of the premium service delivery, solving them was a necessary step to make sure all processes can now run smoothly and, most importantly, all the data related to each phase of the process can be homogeneously stored in the TSP and used to monitor progress. An acceleration in the service provision for the second part of the project life is expected to make up for the accumulated delay, now that the HSbooster.eu service delivery machine and procedures are up and running and services have started being delivered at end of M09 (December 2022).

- **EPE and Project applications:** As already anticipated in sections 3 and 4, version 1 of the application forms for both EPE and projects were reviewed, redesigned and improved in M12. The requested information left too much freedom to the applicant which led to cases where the selected topics of interest or experience were too many to allow a reasonable granularity in the matching process. Also, some fields were not completely aligned in the two forms, with matching being hard to perform at the highest level of detail. Such issues became evident while the allocations were being performed, therefore version 2 of both EPE and project application forms were published at the beginning of March. The applications already received with the old forms were kept unaltered. However, additional information to match the new form requirements is requested so as to align the two “waves” of applicants (old vs new forms) in the best possible way. This will be important to guarantee that all data and statistics are collected homogeneously on the whole population of received applications, regardless of the adopted form.
- **EPE voting:** it was found that missing information in the CVs or lack of details provided in the application forms negatively affected the voting system. On one side, the automated part of the voting provided by the TSP assigned a low score where information was missing or insufficient. On the other hand, the manual part of the voting performed via the qualitative evaluation from partners could not make up for this error as the missing information was not always easy to retrieve online, e.g. consulting the LinkedIn profiles of experts. To solve this issue which risked underestimating the value and experience of experts, a sanity check was performed on received applications. Those presenting incomplete data or CVs were asked to fill in the missing information and submit a more detailed CV in order to revise the voting and consequent expert ranking.
- **EPE-Project mismatch:** Incomplete applications have also led, in a few occasions, to a misinterpretation of the expert profile resulting in a mismatch. The cases in which the selected experts declared they felt not to be a right match with the project (for any reason, including

also possible conflict of interests) the matching was redone and corrected with a new expert selected.

- **First come first served - project application logic:** While the intended method to serve projects is to follow a first come, first served logic, this could not be implemented for applications received in 2022 as services delivery commenced in late December 2022. Since January 2023, the consortium has implemented the first come, first served strategy which has been easier to adopt once the services have started and the pipeline or projects awaiting the matching has shortened.
- **Support to Experts:** Once the services were ready to start, one-to-one kick-off calls with experts were delivered by COMMpla and SGS. These calls have been a key-way to establish personal contact with the expert and to explain the Standard Operating Procedure and expectations. This was an addition to the original pipeline of activities as displayed in D2.1 and D3.1.
- **Shadowing of services:** In order to provide a better support to experts and also gather information and understand better the different types of service delivery a shadowing activity was performed by partners who attended calls between projects and experts to provide information where needed and to monitor the progress of activities as well as grasp insights from the discussions. Information gathered from this have been important in informing partners on how service delivery can be improved and also the type of support that projects are requesting.
- **Delivery of premium services by DS:** In selected cases, the partner Dansk Standards (DS) directly performed services with projects in order to get first-hand experience of:
 - the projects' typical needs and requests
 - the process each expert has to go through to verify clarity of all steps and actions and suggest improvements
- **Delays in service delivery:** While the HSbooster.eu TSP is now up and running and proving to work, service delivery may still sometimes struggle to start on time due to problems with experts (e.g. delays on their side in contacting the projects or lack of proactiveness, failure to promptly update the information on the platform) or projects (e.g. the reference person has changed, the project has changed its interests, has approached the end of its lifecycle or wants to apply some modifications to the objectives of the application). All these cases, which typically represent exceptions, are being treated on a one-to-one basis. The approach followed is to analyse every request separately, discussing within the OCB on the most appropriate action to facilitate the progress of the service.

9. Recommendations

Building on the issues discussed in chapter 8, a set of recommendations for the second half of the project can be derived:

- **Recommendation 1- Monitoring of services:** Services will need to be monitored closely to make sure the information provided in the service report produced by the experts is updated and detailed enough to assess the quality of the service being provided. Monitoring will also need to be done to make sure services are not blocked but can progress and are closed on time

- **Recommendation 2 – Support to Experts:** Experts require guidance to understand how the HSbooster.eu service delivery process works, what the expectations on the activities to be performed with projects are and also reporting requirements. This needs to be intensified especially for experts delivering a service for the first time
- **Recommendation 3 – Recruitment of projects:** The number of received applications is lower than forecast therefore, an additional effort will be made to solicit more applications. A set of actions has been already identified including, as anticipated in chapter 4, using established EC communications channels, reaching out to further contacts of HE, DEP and H2020 projects also exploiting relations with SDOs (e.g. CEN-CENELEC) to access projects they are in contact with, scouting additional projects mentioned in relevant EC documents or initiatives such as the ICT standardisation rolling plan, exploiting synergies with standards related initiatives like StandICT.eu or Stand4EU, setting-up Pay-Per-Click Campaigns (PPC) to improve visibility and positioning of the website and social media posts to attract more visits to the project application page, identifying a set of events, also in geographical areas or topic domains which are under-represented where the consortium of the EAG can attend and promote the Project Open Call.
- **Recommendation 4 – Recruitment of experts:** While the overall number of eligible applications received is satisfactory, there are still some gaps in the areas the experts belong. Relying also on the professional networks of the consortium partners and the EAG members, our recommendation is to contact National Standards Bodies who are active in areas where applications from experts are lower and identify a set of events, also in geographical areas or topic domains which are under-represented.

10. Conclusions

This deliverable has provided a comprehensive overview of the management of open calls, premium service delivery, and monitoring procedures in HSbooster.eu. The digital platform built specifically for the project supports both the open calls for expert recruitment and project attraction, as well as the delivery and monitoring of premium services. Both of these activities are key elements of HSbooster.eu, and the platform has been instrumental in facilitating them.

Moving forward, the Consortium will be focused on implementing the recommendations identified in this report in the best possible way. Additionally, the project team will continue to gather insights and lessons learned to support a continuous improvement approach. The Consortium believes that this proactive approach will allow us to optimise the platform and the procedures it supports, ensuring the continued success of HSbooster.eu.

Consortium

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